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Elçin İBRAHİMOV

Prof. Dr., Karabağ Üniversitesi, Hankendi, Azerbaycan

elchin.ibrahimov@karabakh.edu.az

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14523803>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1105-9345>

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ENDANGERED TURKIC LANGUAGES: IRAN'S LANGUAGE POLICY ON TURKIC LANGUAGES

Abstract

Research about Turkic languages in different Turkic communities has recently started gaining a more objective and sensitive nature in terms of aspect and approach. Attention to endangered languages increased after the 1990s in particular, with research beginning after this time, albeit unsystematically. Certain measures are being taken to protect the languages and national identities of Turkic peoples living in different communities. Countries such as China, Iran, and Russia that have dense Turkic populations keep these languages oppressed by pursuing harsh policies against Turkic peoples. These countries not only fail to guarantee the protection of these languages but also hinder their normal development. The language policies implemented in all three countries and the laws they've adopted related to language have endangered the languages of the few Turkic people living there. The fact that Iran does not guarantee the protection of the languages of the minority Turkic peoples in the state's supreme legislation has made the ability of the Turkic people living in these countries to maintain the existence of their language and culture difficult. This research article attempts to analyze language policies about and against the Turkic people living in Iran and to show ways out of the existing problems.

Keywords: Language Policy, Turkic Societies, Turkic Languages, Endangered Languages, Minority Turkic Peoples.

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TEHLİKEDEKİ TÜRK DİLLERİ: İRAN'DA TÜRK DİLLERİNE İLİŞKİN DİL POLİTİKASI

Özet

Farklı Türk topluluklarında yaşayan Türk dilleri üzerine yapılan araştırmalar son dönemde boyut ve yaklaşım açısından daha objektif ve duyarlı bir nitelik kazanmaya başlamıştır. Özellikle 1990'lı yıllardan sonra tehlikede olan dillere olan ilgi artmış ve bu tarihten sonra daha kapsamlı araştırmalar yapılmaya başlanmıştır.

Günümüzde farklı topluluklarda yaşayan Türk halklarının dillerinin ve milli kimliklerinin korunmasına yönelik bir takım tedbirler alınmaktadır. Türk halklarının yoğun olarak yaşadığı Çin, İran, Rusya gibi ülkeler, Türk halklarına karşı sert bir politika izleyerek bu dilleri baskı altında tutmaktadır. Her üç ülkede de uygulanan dil politikası ve dile ilişkin olarak kabul edilen yasalar, orada yaşayan Türk halklarının dillerini tehlikeye atmıştır. İran'ın üst mevzuatında azınlık Türk halklarının dillerinin devlet tarafından korunmaması, bu ülkelerde yaşayan Türk halklarının kendi dillerinin ve kültürlerinin varlığını sürdürmelerini zorlaştırmaktadır. Bu araştırma yazımızda İran'da yaşayan Türklere yönelik ve onlara karşı uygulanan dil politikasını analiz etmeye ve mevcut sorunlardan çıkış yollarını göstermeye çalışacağız.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Dil Politikası, Türk Topluları, Türk Dilleri, Tehlikedeki Türk Dilleri, Azınlık Türk halkları.

1. Introduction

Turkmen, Khorasan Turks, Qashgais, Khalajs, and Sungurs live in different regions of Iran, mainly Azerbaijani Turks. In addition, Kazakhs, Uzbeks, Afshars, Gajars, Kangars, Karayis, Bayats, Karagozlu, Karakalpaks, Khamsa Turks, Timurtash and a small number of other Turkic peoples also live here.

Today, those who speak South Azerbaijani Turkic are mostly Azerbaijanis who live in Tabriz, northwest of Iran, near the borders of North Azerbaijan, Ardabil, Zanjan, and Gilan. The number of speakers of South Azerbaijani Turkic in Tehran is more than the number of speakers in Tabriz.

South Azerbaijani Turkic is one of the most recognized and scientifically researched ethnic languages in Iran. According to the research of the prominent German researcher Gerard Dorfer, who conducted extensive research on the languages spoken in Iran, we can say that South Azerbaijani Turkic occupies a special place among the languages of this country. South Azerbaijani Turkic and its present-day position in Iran is an extensive and separate research topic in itself. In this study, we will try to talk about the current situation of South Azerbaijani Turkic. As noted by G. Dorfer, Iran is one of the most recently discovered regions of the world in terms of linguistic research.

As we know, there is an overt or hidden language policy and language planning that puts the languages of the minority peoples of the countries in the background, determines the priority of the standard language, and regulates the conditions of use of the languages that remain in the background within the political borders. Professor Suer Eker divides this policy and language planning into

“monolingualism (France, Turkey), egalitarian multilingualism (Belgium) and national/regional (India)” (Eker, 2008: 190). Today, in Iran, which is a theocratic country from a political point of view, language planning and implementation are continued based on the principle of monolingualism.

In response to those who called their mother tongue “foreign language” and “local language”, the eminent scientist Dr. Javad Hayet wrote in his article, “Today's language of Azerbaijani Turks is Turkic. The language of every nation is the language it learns in the arms of its mother” (Gökdağ, 2007: 70). Because the Azerbaijani language expression has a narrow meaning. Thus, the Turkic language used in Azerbaijan has been used for centuries by millions of people not only here, but also in the Persian regions of Iran. The term “Azerbaijani language” shortens the region of development of this language. This language was called the Turkic language until the 1930s. In his article, Javad Heyat said, “Our language is called Turkic in Iran. Our language has been called Turkic since ancient times. European Turkologists also call our language Azerbaijani Turkic or Azeri Turkic. Calling Ottoman or Anatolian Turkic of Turkey the Turkic language should not prevent our language from being called by the same name” (Heyet, 1993: 71).

In the article “On the name and position of the Azerbaijani Turkic language”, J. Hayet notes: “Based on the history of the Turkic language, the Turkic peoples, the place of the Azerbaijani Turkic language, the ethnic division of the Azerbaijani Turks and the folk literature, we conclude that the Turkic-speaking people in Iran are not Turkic-speaking at the moment. , is Turkic in every respect” (Heyet, 1993: 94).

G. Dorfer, a German scholar who is a serious researcher of the language and history of Iranian Turks, notes that “Iran was under the rule of Turkic dynasties (and Turkic armies) for about a thousand years, which caused a certain degree of resentment” (Dorfer, 2008: 7).

1.1. Methods

Therefore, it can be suggested that anger and resentment towards the long-term rule of the Turks played a certain role in the re-formation of Persian nationalism in Iran starting from the 19th century and its transformation into the ideology of the state. Modern Persian nationalism, whose ideological foundations were mostly laid by non-Persian intellectuals, came to power in 1924 with the overthrow of the Qajar dynasty and became the dominant ideology during the Pahlavi period. Fatali Shah's son Jalaladdin Mirza Qajar, S. Hasan Taghizadeh, H. Kazimzadeh Iranshahr-Tabrizi, Mahmud Afshar, S. Ahmed Kasravi, A. Turkic intellectuals such as Azad Maragai, Taqi Arani, Timurtash, D. Rizazade Shafaq, and representatives of other rights such as Mirza Melkum Khan (Armenian), Malikul-Shuara Bahar (Georgian), M. Ali Furughi (Jewish) were pioneers of Persian nationalism in Iran.

After determining the names of the Turks in Iran, determining the position of the state is important in clarifying the general situation.

The shortest definition of the term mother tongue is “the language learned from the mother or the closest environment”, and today there are thousands of mother tongues in the world at the “spoken language” level. Only a few of them were able to pass from the spoken language to the written language. Turkic is one such language, and the scope of today's Turkic language has a history of at least 1,500 years of uninterrupted written language or written language.

S. Barutçu Özöndar notes in this regard: “The main factor in the transition of a spoken language to a written language is the purposeful policy of the state in this field” (Barutçu, 1999: 33). The Turks ruled Iran for about ten centuries and established strong states. The Seljuk and Safavid empires are at the top of these. During the period of the Turkic rulers, Turkic was the state language, the language of

the court, and the language of the army, while Persian was mainly used in correspondence and literature. However, after the Pahlavi period, Turkic handed over the status of the state, court, and army language to Persian and lost all its official status (Ibrahimov, 2020: 31).

B. Bekbabayi notes in this regard: “The book “History of the Turkic Language and Dialects” published by Dr. Javad Hayat in 1985 and 1986 was published by President S. A. Although Khamenei and Prime Minister M. H. Mousavi were honored with official letters of thanks and evaluated as a great service to the Turkic language and culture, it was evaluated by the panelists as a dangerous step towards the division of Iran” (Bicbabayi, 2012: 89).

Although Persian is the official language in Iran and all correspondence is conducted in Persian, Turkic is spoken in all official structures of Turkic regions. For example, defendants who are Turkic are judged in Turkic, communication is conducted in Turkic in offices, contacts are established, Turkic is often spoken in classes, etc. In other regions, when Turks get together, they usually prefer to speak Turkic, even if they are surrounded by speakers of other languages, the situation does not change and Turks continue to speak Turkic.

Ethnic groups living in Iran have linguistic and cultural ties with their compatriots living in neighboring countries. We can say that the relations between the Republic of Azerbaijan, which gained its independence in 1991, and Iran are very good. However, we should also note that Iran is sensitive to these relations. There are also natural reasons for this. Because the expansion of relations between South and North Azerbaijan and, as a result, the increase in the consciousness of Turkicness and Azerbaijaniness in Iran is the most important factor affecting the relations between the two countries. The Iranian state understands very well what processes the further expansion and diversification of these relations will bring forth in the future. However, despite all this, the cultural ties between the Turks of Azerbaijan living in the north and the south are getting stronger day by day and the historical unity is preserved. M. S. Erol in his article “Iran's Central Asian Policy” says that “the Turkic elements in Iran, especially the Azerbaijani and Turkmen Turks, create problems in this country's position towards the Turkic republics” (Gökdağ, 2007: 63).

Mohammad Khatami, who won the presidential elections in 1997 with the slogan “Iran belongs to all Iranians”, failed to fulfill his promises and faced a serious loss of votes in non-Persian regions in the presidential elections he participated in for the second time.

Before the June 8, 2001, presidential election, a group of Azerbaijani MPs, scientists, and intellectuals wrote a petition to M. Khatami, saying that “we all have to accept that Iran belongs to all Iranians, not just a certain group” and demanded more rights for mother tongues in education and broadcasting. they did Such desires are gradually increasing due to the current president Hassan Rouhani's slogan of “Measure and restraint” and his promises to ethnic minorities.

1.2. Expectations

Even though the Turks living together with the Persians were subjected to serious assimilation, we can say that in the regions where they are the majority, the consciousness of Turkicness has become stronger. In the past 30 years, the points that played an active role in the rapid development of national consciousness among the Turks of Iran and South Azerbaijan in particular can be summarized as follows:

- Along with nearly a thousand-year rule of the Turks in Iran, the national consciousness chose a new direction with the Azerbaijan National Government established between 1945 and 1946. The relative freedom was achieved after the overthrow of the Pahlavi regime and the

establishment of the Islamic Republic of Iran. Publication of books, newspapers, and journals in the Turkic language, especially the possibility of continuous publication of "Varlig" journal for the last 30 years.

- The collapse of the Soviet Union, the independence of Northern Azerbaijan, and the wide viewing of Turkic and Azerbaijani television channels in Iran via satellite. After the election of M. Khatami as president in the 1997 elections, the increase of programs in Turkic, was the beginning of student movements demanding personal and public rights and freedoms.
- In 2006, an Iranian newspaper insulted the Turks and the uprising of many Turkic cities, especially Tabriz. The actions of the fans of the football team "Traktorsazi", which has increasingly become a symbol of Iranian Turks, in the stands to convey and defend their cultural and linguistic rights. Demonstration of national unity and solidarity of Turks during the East Azerbaijan earthquake in August 2012.
- The expansion of the virtual world and the widespread use of social networks. Turkic intellectuals also appreciate these opportunities.

1.3. Discussion

Samad Sardariniya tried to prove that "the Turks in Iran are socially advanced in all cultural fields" in his book "Tabriz First City" (Serdariniya, 2005: 14). Still, even though the Turks have a deep-rooted culture, the policy of humiliation and humiliation (according to the intellectuals, British policy) that began with racist thinking during the Pahlavi period continues. As a result of the state's urban growth and urbanization policy, the Turks who came from the Turkic villages and settled in Tehran and its surroundings at first could not get used to the city life and continued their simple village customs and behaviors. Politicians also took advantage of this situation to conduct humiliating and insulting campaigns against Turks through the media, especially television. This also played an important role in the assimilation of Turks. The Turks could not prevent this process, but in many cases accepted the current situation and directly participated in the acceleration of the assimilation process. Using derogatory expressions against Turkic society, adding anecdotes, etc. such forms of behavior are considered the results of the mentioned social psychological fact (Ibrahimov, 2020: 114).

In 2000-2001, when the need to revise the Arabic alphabet was felt, two separate orthographic meetings were held in Tehran. In this meeting, the name of the language (Turkic language), the name of the alphabet, spelling of vowels and consonants, diphthongs, hamza, compound words, and other such issues were discussed, the project prepared by the scientific staff were distributed to the participants and decisions were made by secret voting, and the results were 3 people analyzed by the commission.

In 1979, after the overthrow of the Shah's regime and the establishment of the Islamic Republic of Iran, there was a sudden jump in the number of printed media and books published in Turkic. From the excitement of publishing dozens of newspapers and journals in their mother tongue, in the early years, they preferred articles that strengthened national consciousness. The Society of Tabriz Poets and Writers, which was established immediately after the revolution, published articles promoting the revolution in the Turkic language in the press organ "Ülker" in the early 1980s. Again, during these years, the Society of Young Poets and Writers in Tabriz published a press organ called "Youth" in the same direction. Azerbaijan Society of Poets and Writers, founded in Tehran in April 1979, published the collection "Sun" in February 1981. "Azerbaijan Culture Society, which started its activities in Tehran in March 1979, was founded under the leadership of the famous poet Habib Sahir. "Yoldash", "On the Revolution" and many other journals were suspended several times by the regime because they included Marxist views along with articles touching on the problems and aspirations of Iranian Turks" (Gökdağ,

2015: 401).

In Tehran, a group investigating Azerbaijani issues was publishing the “Chanlibel” newspaper. Some independent journals that were not connected to any group or party also started to be published during this period. “Varlıg” published under the leadership of Javad Heyat, “Dade Gorgud” journals published in Tabriz, and the Turkic column headed by the famous poet Yahya Sheydan in the newspaper “Furuğü-azadi” have done important work in the way of Turkic culture. During the 50-year rule of the Pahlavis, intellectuals who faced publication censorship published dozens of journals and hundreds of books in the first years of the revolution. In addition to the above-mentioned journals and newspapers, some journals and newspapers, some of them in Turkic and Persian, were also published. For example, “Odlar Yurdu”, “Ulduz”, “Araz” newspapers, “Molla Nasreddin”, “Dade Gorgud” journals in Tabriz, “Vatan dinzidzhan” newspapers in Sarab, “Azadlig”, “Koroghlu”, “Voice of Azerbaijan” in Tehran. journals were published. Most of these journals were published between 1979 and 1980, and many of them were able to produce only a few issues, some were closed due to financial difficulties, and some were closed due to pressure from the Iranian leadership and various excuses. Only “Varlıg” journal continues its publication until today” (Gökdağ, 2007: 59).

The first issue of “Varlıg” journal was published in April 1979 in Tehran. About 20 percent of the articles are published in Persian. The first issues of the journal are published in the “social-cultural journal” category. In the first years, the journal was published once a month, later it was published every two months and three months. During the years when “Varlıg” journal was published, the literary language of Iranian Turks was not fully formed. There was no uniform norm in the matter of spelling and punctuation marks. After the revolution, the process of updating the written language based on the literary language of Northern Azerbaijan began. In the beginning, the journal gradually eliminated the language and style problem and made the words written in the Arabic alphabet easy to read. The journal, which includes the common words used by Turks, took over the task of the “Tarjuman” newspaper printed by Ismayil Bey Gaspıralı a hundred years ago. At that time, contrary to the supporters of taking the Tabriz dialect as a literary language, “Varlıg” journal acted on the principle that “one nation cannot have two written languages” and tried to apply the literary language used in Northern Azerbaijan by changing words of Russian origin. The editors of the journal, especially J. Hayet, and H. Nitqi, tried to create a Turkic language that could be understood both in Azerbaijan (South and North) and Turkey by adding some words and terms from Azerbaijani and Turkey Turkish” (Gökdağ, 2007: 59).

Apart from Azerbaijani Turks, other Turkic peoples also live in Iran. It would be appropriate to give brief information about them from the point of view of forming a certain idea about the distribution area, the status of their language, and the general situation of those Turkic peoples.

2. Khalaj Turkic

Foreign orientalists V. Minorski and G. Dörfer, and Iranian researchers M. Moghaddam have conducted important studies on the Iranian Khalajs and their language and identified the characteristics of this dialect.

M. Muqaddam collected language materials related to Vafas, Ashtian, and Tafrash dialects in this region, investigated their similar and different characteristics with Khalaj and Azerbaijani languages, and published the results of the research in Tehran in 1940 in “İrankude” journal.

V. Minorsky published the results of his research on Khalaj Turkic in London in 1940 under the title “The Turkic of Khalaj” in the “Bulletin of the Society of Oriental and African Studies” journal (Minorsky, 1940: 417).

Professor G. Dorfer of the University of Göttingen, Germany, after getting acquainted with the

research of M. Muqaddam and V. Minorsky, decided to visit the regions of Iran inhabited by the Khalajs and study the language of the Khalajs. G. Dörfer, who came to Iran with a delegation in 1969, published the results of his research in 1971 under the name "Khalaj materials" in comparison with the writings of M. Muqaddam. This book is written in English and published in America by the Department of Ural-Altaic Studies of Indiana University. In his book, G. Dörfer gave a part of M. Muqaddam's Persian book in the form of a manuscript. The research and publications of the team organized by G. Dorfer about the Khalaj language continued later, and the articles of G. Dorfer and his colleagues (Prof. Semih Tezcan and others) were published in German, English, and Turkic (Turkey Turkish).

Khalaj Turkic is one of the most endangered languages in Iran today. Research scientists and poets (writers) from the Khalaj Turks criticized the Iranian government's neglect of the preservation of the Khalaj Turkic language and stated that this language and culture is rapidly weakening and is on the verge of extinction.

A. Jamrasi gave a speech on this issue at the event held by the Gum Research Foundation on "Khalaj Turkic literature and history". In Jamrasi's speech, "Currently, Khalajs live in 60 villages of Qum and central provinces. In recent years, young families do not teach their children the Khalaj language for various reasons. As a result, the number of 45,000 people speaking Khalaj Turkic in 1979 decreased to 19,000 in 2010. According to research, currently, only 5 out of 100 Khalaj families teach their children the ancient Khalaj Turkic language" (Hatami, 2020).

Another southern sociologist, B. Hatami, in his research on the Khalajs, notes that the language and culture of the Khalaj Turks are rapidly weakening. B. Hatami, a graduate of Ankara Hacettepe University, commented on the language, culture, history, and social life of Khalaj Turks living in the central provinces of Iran and the Qum region in an interview with "Voice of America". According to the sociologist, "Khalajs generally live in Qum, Central and Tehran provinces alongside other Turkic regions of Iranian Azerbaijan, including Shahsevans (Shasavan)" (Hatami, 2020). He states that approximately 66 thousand Khalaj Turks live in these regions.

B. Hatami, who visited the regions where the Khalaj Turks lived while conducting a study called "Social and cultural life of the Khalaj Turks", emphasizes that the Khalaj people are subject to more assimilation compared to other Turkic peoples living in Iran. According to him, the Khalaj community is discriminated against by both Persians and other Turkic communities living in Iran-Azerbaijan.

"Khalajs feel isolated from other Turks in public life. It's like a psychology left to them from their ancestors. For example, in regions where khalajs and private people live together, khalajs work in different fields. At the same time, they are known for having an exuberant and fighting spirit," says the sociologist (Hatami, 2020).

Khalaj Turkic is listed as a vulnerable language in the list of endangered languages published by UNESCO. However, as a person who went to Khalajistan and interacted with the Khalaj people, I can say that the current situation of the Khalaj people and the Khalaj language is more deplorable than what is stated in the UNESCO statement. Because Khalaj Turkic is almost not spoken among the children of Khalaj in Iran today. Most of the people who know this language are elderly people. It is from this point of view that there is a very high probability that Khalaj Turkic will disappear shortly.

3. Qashqai Turkic

Qashqai Turkic is one of the Turkic languages spoken by approximately 1.5 million Qashqais living in Iran today and belongs to the Oghuz group. Currently, the Qashgais live mainly in the region known for a long time as “Vilayeti-Qashgai” - in the present-day Fars province, as well as in Khuzistan, Boyer-Ahmed provinces, around the cities of Isfahan, Shiraz, and Firuzabad.

The Qashqai Turks are a Turkic people who migrated from Turkestan, Caucasus, Azerbaijan, and Anatolia to the center of Iran and then to the south in the 13th century. The Qashgais gradually became stronger and became one of the ruling communities of the region during the rule of the Elkhans.

M. A. In 1912, Rasulzadeh “notes that the Qashqai lived a nomadic life in the grasslands in the summer months and in the winter months in the winter months, their number was about 350 thousand” (Rasulzadeh, 2013: 14).

According to the official data of the Iranian Statistical Center, in 2011, the population of Shiraz city was 1.6 million, and the population of Fars province was 4.5 million. The Qashqais make up 60% of the population of Fars province, mostly living in 29 cities (mostly Abada, Sipidan, Bavanat, Hunch, Shiraz, Kazerun, Kawar, Firuzabad, Neyriz, Chehrum, etc.). Based on this, it is possible to say that there are more than 2.8 million Qashqai Turks.

The researchers researching Qashgai Turkic called this language Oghuz, Azerbaijan, Afshar, etc. explained as a branch of languages.

Today, Dilek Arenoglu Ataizi, who seriously and comprehensively researches the language of the Qashgai Turks, provides important information in his work “The Language of the Qashgai Turks”: “Although the Qashgai Turkic is included in the languages of the Oghuz group, Azerbaijani, Turkmen, Khamsa, Khorasan, who live in the same region and belong to the same language group differs from the languages of the Turks. Qashqai Turkic appears to be a dialect of Azerbaijani Turkic” (Erenoglu, 2018: 53).

When G. Dorfer classified the languages belonging to the Oghuz group, he included the Qashqais in the Southern Oghuz group (Qashqai Turkic and dialects close to the language). G. Dorfer also noted that there are many transitional languages (dialects) between southern Oghuz and central Oghuz (Azerbaijani Turkic).

Y. Kalafat mentions that “Qashgai Turkic has the same roots as Azerbaijani Turkic and the Istanbul dialect used by the Western Oghuz Turks and used an alphabet of 40 letters until the time of Nadir Shah² (Kalafat, 2005: 33).

N. Özkan notes that “the Qashqais speak a language that is close to Azerbaijani Turkic and at the same time has the influence of Khalaj and Bayat dialects, and although they know Persian well, they turn to Persian only when necessary” (Rafael, 1997: 237).

B. A. Gokdag considers the “Turkic language spoken in countries such as the Balkan Peninsula, Turkey, Iran, Iraq, Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Northern Cyprus within Oghuz. He considers it necessary to accept the Turkic language (except Khalaj Turkic in Iran) as dialects of Oghuzkan” (Gökdog, 2015: 55).

According to Muhitdin Çelik, who wrote a doctoral dissertation on Qashgai Turkic, various opinions have been put forward about the language spoken by Qashgai Turks, but until now, no definite opinion has been given about which branch of the Turkic language the language spoken by Qashgai Turks belongs to.

Most of the Qashqais are bilingual, they speak Persian as well as Turkic, the dominant and official language of the country. Education reform, which considers compulsory education for all Qashqai children, is a major factor in the spread of bilingualism.

The vast majority of Qashqais live in limited socio-economic conditions among the inhabitants of different ethnolinguistic groups of different peoples of Iran. The use of Persian in daily communication and conversation is more common among young people. At the same time, the fact that the Persian language is the hegemonic and widespread language in the fields of education and work limits the use of their mother tongue by the Qashqais living in the cities. Qashqai is a language suitable for a nomadic lifestyle. In other words, Qashqai was formed to meet the needs of Qashqai Turks, who lived a nomadic life for a long time.

The fact that the Qashqais gave up the nomadic life and lived in the cities led to the loss of the importance of their mother tongue and as a result, it was replaced by the Persian language. Thus, Qashqai has descended to the level of a language used only at home, in the family. This may result in the danger and extinction of the kashaya in the future.

4. Khorasan Turkic

Khorasan Turks live in the provinces of South Khorasan and Razavi Khorasan, located in the northeast of Iran. Although there is no official information about the number of Khorasan Turks in the province, the total number of Khorasan Turks is 1.5-2 million in the research conducted on this topic. Khorasan Turkic, which was previously mistakenly considered Turkmen, was attributed by G. Dorfer to the eastern branch of the Oghuz group after extensive research in this field. In this regard, G. Dörfer notes: "Khorasan Turkic can be divided into two (northern and southern) or four (southwestern, northeastern, central and southern) subgroups" (Doerfer, 1998: 273).

In Iran, the level of use of Khorasan Turks' mother tongue and their attitude towards their mother tongue varies from province to province. For example, Khorasan Turkic is widely used in daily life in cities such as Bocrurd, Kuchan, and Daregaz, but in cities such as Nishapur, Mashhad, and Sabzavar, it is only used in a limited way in family communication. The presence of different ethnic groups, demographics, and socio-economic conditions are considered determining factors in the degree of use of the mother tongue and attitude to the mother tongue. The vast majority of Khorasan Turks are bilingual, but bilingualism is gradually turning into monolingualism in favor of the Persian language. "The widespread use of the Persian language in social and cultural life has led to the loss of the function of the Khorasan Turkic language, the gradual reduction and limitation of its field of use" (Rafael, 1997: 136).

The Turks of Khorasan, like other Turkic peoples living in Iran, were subjected to assimilation within the framework of Iran's "nation-state" project after the Pahlavi came to power (1925).

Although Khorasan Turkic has been studied to a certain extent, there is not enough information about the geography and linguistic features of this language. Much of the history of Iran, which includes the features of the transitional period of languages, has not yet been sufficiently explored. Many Turks here (especially men) know two languages. The Turkic population is growing rapidly. Today, the Turkic population of Khorasan is about two million. G. Dorfer notes that Khorasan Turks call themselves "Torki, unlike Turkmen and others" (Dorfer, 2008: 100).

The languages of the Khorasan Turks are listed in the list of weakly endangered languages in the 2nd and 3rd degree out of six danger levels according to the endangered languages program in the criteria defined by UNESCO.

Until recently, the Turks living in Khorasan gradually fell into the position of a minority people, although the area of use of this language narrowed, the new factors brought out by globalization, the collapse of the Soviet Union in the 1990s, led to the rise of national consciousness in Iranian Turkicness in general, especially in the Turks living in Khorasan, and the Turkic language, had a positive effect on the protection of the Turkic identity.

However, the danger has not disappeared. Many languages of Turkic origin are in danger of disappearing in Iran. This is because the Persian language is the only official language of Iran, which brings with it the process of Persianization, as well as the fact that teaching in the mother tongue is not allowed. Currently, the Turkic people living in Iran are facing the threat of losing their oral and written cultural values. Lack of job opportunities forces Turks to move from villages and regions to big cities. In this regard, migration is one of the main factors accelerating the assimilation of Turks.

5. Sungur Turkic

Sungur Turkic is one of the languages of the Turkic people living in Iran. It is the native language of the people living in the small town of Sungur and its surrounding villages (Qaleyi-Farhad Khan and Gurve) located 83 km northeast of Kermanshah.

The word Sungur is explained in "Divani lüğat-it Türk" as one of the "birds of prey" and "birds of prey" (Atıcı, 2015: 530). In "Gutadgu-bilik" the word was changed to "sunğur" (to be precise: ğ) and called "sungur bird" (Arat, 2015: 409). The word "Sungur" is shown in the new explanatory dictionary of Turkic as "sunğur, sunğar, şunğur, sunğur" with different phonetic features (Dilchin, 1983: 194).

Sungur Turkic was first studied and published in the form of an article by the American orientalist G. Windfuhr and later by G. Dorfer, a tireless researcher of the languages of the minority Turkic peoples in Iran. In this sub-chapter, we will try to talk about sungurs comparatively with both the research of Javad Hayat and the writings of G. Dorfer. I should also mention that the Kurds who moved there during the Iran-Iraq war also live in the region where the Sungurs live in Iran, and the residents of that region speak three languages (Turkic, Kurdish, and Persian).

The most recent serious research on the Sungur Turks and the Turkic language belongs to Christian Bulut. K. Bulut mentioned the term sungur as "songor" (Bulut, 2005: 241). In the research conducted in the region, it was determined that the Sungur Turks living in the city of Sungur pronounce the mentioned word as "sunğur" or "sunğur".

According to the 1991 census, the number of Sungurs was 37,772. Currently, 40-50 thousand people speak Sungur Turkic. K. Bulut notes about Sungur Turkic: "Sungur Turkic is a unique language and it has no direct connection with any of the close Turkic languages" (Bulut, 2005: 241).

I. Kazimov notes that "the second component of sungur is related to the general ethnic name "gur" (famous Hun tribes: Onogur, Saragur, Uighur, Utigur, Kurtigur, etc.)" (Kazimov, 2016: 169).

M. Shiraliyev says that "instead of s in the ancient Kypchak-Turkic monuments and in the modern Kypchak group of Turkic languages, the use of the sound sh instead of s shows that the sh element reflected in our toponymy is the Kypchak-type Savir-Khazar, which played a key role in the formation of the national spoken language of Azerbaijan in the early Middle Ages. are elements of language unions" (Shiraliyev, 1965: 15).

M. Musaoglu notes in this regard: "Sonkor language or Turkic is used as a native language at the level of colloquial language, it is spoken by only 35 thousand people in the city of Sonkor in Iran and Farhad, Khan residence. Since the language in question does not have the level of a literary

language, it can be considered a dialect of the common Turkic language or Oghuz” (Musayev, 2012: 39).

I. Kazimov said, “The language of the Sungurs is also used as a means of communication between the Turkic and Kurdish peoples. Speakers of other Turkic dialects of Iran also understand this language and speak with each other” (Kazimov, 2016: 33).

The Sungur Turks, who live in isolation in their region, mainly speak Sungur Turkic and Kurdish, which are already dominant languages in the province. Especially in recent years, the Persian language has gained a strong reputation among Sungur Turks. “Sungur Turkic belongs to the southern Oghuz or Afshar dialect group” (Heyet, 1993: 676).

Sungur Turks are facing the threat of extinction of their language as they are left out of the region where Turks live. The use of the Persian language as the official written language and the language of education limited the existence of Sungur Turkic only within the framework of oral traditions.

As in the whole of Iran, the language of education in the region where the Sungurs live is Persian. All stages of education are conducted in the Persian language. Therefore, Sungur Turks living in the region receive their education in the Persian language. Sungur Turkic is a language of oral communication only, it is not used in correspondence.

In addition, the Turkic researcher A. Atıcı completed his doctoral dissertation on “Sungur Turkic”, collected the necessary documents and information, and published it (Atıcı, 2015: 492).

Like other minority Turkic peoples in Iran, the threat of the disappearance of Sungur Turkic should be prevented, and folklore and language materials should be identified and written down before they are forgotten.

6. Result

In conclusion, we can say that the fact that Iran and South Azerbaijan were under the rule of Turks for a long time is an important issue from the Turkological point of view. The history, dialects, languages, and folklore of this region should be thoroughly explored. The culture, traditions, ethnography, and languages of the few Turkic peoples living in Iran should also be widely studied.

Turks live mostly in the northwest of Iran. While the presence and usage of the mother tongue is wide in the regions with dense Turkic populations, Turks living in scattered and small groups face problems in keeping their mother tongue alive. The fact that the official language of Iran is Persian and that Persian is the hegemonic language in every field makes it difficult for Turkic peoples to use their mother tongue. For this reason and as a result, it is important to determine the situation, collect the necessary materials for the analysis of the level of mixing of languages, release the risk of extinction of languages, and take measures to continue their existence.

There is a need for the Iranian state to take into account the current situation and change the policy of isolation and assimilation that has been carried out for years against the minority Turkic peoples. Otherwise, it will not be possible to continue the policy of assimilation, discrimination, and censorship against a nation of 35 million for a long time.

Today, certain measures are being taken to protect the languages and national identities of the Turkic peoples living in different societies. The failure to provide state protection of the languages of the minority Turkic peoples in the supreme legislation and constitutions of the Russian Federation, the People's Republic of China, and the Islamic Republic of Iran makes it difficult for the Turkic people living in these countries to

continue the existence of their language and culture. However, the language policy of the Turkic people living in the Republic of Moldova, Bulgaria, and Georgia related to language and national identity issues can be considered satisfactory. Today, the policy of isolation against the Turkic communities is carried out for certain political purposes in the countries where a small number of Turkic peoples mainly live. Countries such as China, Iran, and Russia keep these languages under pressure by pursuing a harsh policy against the Turkic peoples, not to mention not guaranteeing the protection of these languages, they even hinder their normal development. The language policy implemented in all three countries and the laws adopted related to language have endangered the languages of the few Turkic people living there. At present, a small number of Turkic languages in other countries of the world (mainly Moldova, Bulgaria, Georgia, Latvia, Hungary, Mongolia, China, etc.) are facing the threat of extinction.

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ÇIKAR ÇATIŞMASI BEYANI

Yazarın/Yazarların herhangi bir çıkara dayalı ilişkisi bulunmamaktadır.

ETİK ONAY/KATILIMCI ONAMI

Makale kapsamında katılımcı kullanılmadığı için ilgili onaya yer verilmemiştir.

MADDİ DESTEK

Çalışma için herhangi bir maddi destek alınmamıştır.

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